

Formulation and Evaluation of Hybrid Mucoadhesive Tablets of Antifungal Agent of Miconazole Nitrate

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ABSTRACT - The main objective of research work is to develop hybrid mucoadhesive drug delivery systems for oral and vaginal candidiasis. A hybrid mucoadhesive drug delivery system is a unique dosage form, wherein the same mucoadhesive tablets can be delivered through multiple routes, through oral/vaginal route for candidiasis. The effectiveness of the specialized drug delivery systems has been enhanced with the use of different combination of polymers in the form of Interpolyelectrolyte complex (IPEC).

KEYWORDS - *Hybrid Mucoadhesive Tablet, Mucoadhesive vaginal tablet, Interpolyelectrolyte complex (IPEC), Candidiasis.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Mucoadhesive drug delivery system interact with mucus layer covering the mucosal epithelial surface and mucin molecules and increase the residence time of dosage form at the site of absorption. They facilitate an intimate contact of dosage forms with underlying absorption surface and thus improve the therapeutic performance of drug. In recent years, many such many such Mucoadhesive drug delivery system have been developed for, oral, buccal, and vaginal routes for both systemic and local effect.¹

Oral route of administration of drug is most preferred to the patient and the clinician. However, per oral administration of drug has a disadvantage such as hepatic first pass metabolism and enzymatic degradation within the GI tract, prohibit oral administration of many drugs. Transmucosal routes of drug delivery offers distinct advantages over per oral administration for systemic drug delivery. These advantages include possible bypass of first pass metabolism effect, avoidance of presystemic elimination within the GI tract and depending on the particular drug, a better enzymatic flora for drug absorption. The buccal region offers attractive route of administration for systemic and local drug delivery.

The mucosa has a rich blood supply and is permeable to many pharmacologically active agents. Further oral transmucosal drug delivery by pass first pass effect. Therefore preferred site for retentive oral transmucosal delivery system and for sustained and controlled release delivery is the buccal mucosa.²

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

S.No	Materials	Suppliers
1	Miconazole nitrate	Yarrow chem., Mumbai.
2	Chitosan	Himedia laboratories Pvt Ltd.
3	Carbopol 971P	Yarrow Chem, Mumbai.
4	Polycarbophil	Yarrow Chem, Mumbai.
5	Microcrystalline cellulose	Yarrow Chem, Mumbai.
6	Talc	Karnataka Fine Chem.
7	Barium sulphate	Yarrow Chem, Mumbai.
8	NaOH	Karnataka Fine Chem.
9	Bovine serum albumin	Karnataka Fine Chem.
10	KOH	Yarrow Chem. Mumbai.
11	Potassium Dihydrogen phosphate	Karnataka Fine Chem.
12	Calcium hydroxide	Karnataka Fine Chem.
13	Lactic acid	Karnataka Fine Chem.
14	Acetic acid	Karnataka Fine Chem.
15	Glucose	Karnataka Fine Chem.
16	Urea	Yarrow Chem Mumbai.

2.2 Method of preparation:

Mucoadhesive hybrid tablets containing miconazole nitrate were prepared by direct compression technique. Different formulations of mucoadhesive hybrid tablet were prepared using specified amount of polymers and other excipients. Before going for direct compression, the entire powder blend including drug polymer and excipients were thoroughly blended in mortar and pestle for about 15 minutes. After sufficient mixing of powder blend lubricant talc was added and again mixed for additional 5 minutes. The mixture was then compressed using 6mm flat faced punch on single stroke tablet compression machine.

2.3 Preformulation study

Preformulation study is one of the important prerequisite in development of any drug delivery system. Thus a Preformulation study was carried out to check the capability between drug and selected polymers used and development of analytical method of drug.

2.4 Drug Identification

The identifications of drug were determined by using following methods.

2.4.1 Melting point method

Melting point of the drug was determined by using Micro-controller based melting point apparatus (Chemline CL-725). Any lowering or widening of melting point from its range exhibits impurity.

2.4.2 Fourier Transfer Infra-Red Spectroscopy.

Drug miconazole nitrate was identified by using Fourier Transfer Infra- Red Spectroscopy by Comparing with the standard reference spectra.

2.4.3 Determination of absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of miconazole nitrate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

For this determination about 100mg of drug miconazole nitrate was weighed and dissolved in 100ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 in a 100ml volumetric flask. Then this was further diluted by phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and was analyzed in UV spectrophotometer between 200-400nm. The point of absorption maximum obtained in graph was considered as λ_{max} of the pure drug.

2.4.4 Determination of absorption maximum (λ_{max}) of Miconazole nitrate in simulated vaginal fluid pH 4.2.

About 100mg of drug miconazole nitrate was weighed and dissolved in 100ml of simulated vaginal fluid pH 4.2 in a 100ml volumetric flask. This was further diluted by SVF pH 4.2 and analyzed in UV visible spectrophotometer between 200-400nm. The point of absorption maximum obtained in the graph was considered as λ_{max} of the pure drug.

2.4.5 Drug- Excipients Compatibility studies

Compatibility studies were carried out to know the possible interactions between miconazole nitrate and excipients used in the formulation. Physical mixture of drug and Excipients were prepared to study the Compatibility. Drug polymer compatibility studies were carried out using FTIR spectroscopy. IR spectrum of pure drug and polymers was seen 600-4000 cm^{-1} .

2.5 Characterization of the chitosan-carbopol 971P IPEC

Characterization of the chitosan-carbopol 971P IPEC was done by using FTIR. For this purpose FTIR spectra was taken for Chitosan and carbopol alone in 1000 cm^{-1} - 2000 cm^{-1} and 1400 cm^{-1} - 1800 cm^{-1} followed by IPEC formed were also seen in same IR range of 1000 cm^{-1} - 2000 cm^{-1} and then in 1400 cm^{-1} - 1800 cm^{-1} respectively. Thus IPEC formed were confirmed by little shift in IR peaks of IPEC due to formation of new bold NH_3 which was formed due to protonation of amine group of chitosan.

2.6 Preparation of buffer solutions^{3, 4}

2.6.1 Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8)³

50ml of 0.2M potassium dihydrogen phosphate was taken 200ml of volumetric flask, to which 22.4 ml of 0.2M sodium hydroxide solutions was added and then the volume was made upto mark with distilled water.

2.6.2 Simulated vaginal fluid (SVF)⁴

Simulated vaginal fluid (SVF) was prepared as reported : 3.51 g/l NaCl , 1.40 g/l KOH, 0.222 g/l, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, 0.018 g/l bovine serum albumin (BSA), 2g/l lactic acid, 1g/l CH_3COOH , 0.16 g/l glycerol, 0.4g/l urea and 5g/l glucose. Then pH was adjusted at 4.2 by using 0.1 N HCl.

2.6.30.2 M Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate

27.281 gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was added to 1000ml volumetric flask containing distilled water and volume was made upto the mark with distilled water.

2.6.40.2M Sodium hydroxide

8gm of NaOH was taken in a 1000ml volumetric flask containing distilled water and volume was made upto the mark with distilled water.

2.7 Preparation of calibration curve of miconazole nitrate

2.7.1 Preparation of calibration curve of miconazole nitrate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 solutions.

Exactly weighed 100mg of miconazole nitrate was dissolved in 100ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (Miconazole nitrate stock-1). From the stock- 1, 10ml is withdrawn and made upto 100ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (Miconazole stock-2). From the standard stock-2 aliquots of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5ml were taken in five different 10ml volumetric flask and the volume was made upto 10ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to get 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration solutions respectively. They are then analyzed at 272nm against blank of phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

2.7.2 Preparation of calibration curve of miconazole nitrate in simulated vaginal fluid (SVF) pH 4.2 solutions.

Exactly weighed 100mg of miconazole nitrate was dissolved in 100ml of SVF pH 4.2. (Miconazole nitrate stock-1). From the stock-1 10ml was withdrawn and made upto 100ml with SVF pH 4.2 (Miconazole nitrate stock- 2). From the standard stock-2 aliquots of 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1, 1.25ml were taken in 5 different 10ml volumetric flask and the volume was made upto 10ml with SVF pH 4.2 to get 25, 50, 75, 100, 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ concentration solutions respectively. They are then analyzed at 272nm against blank of SVF pH 4.2.

2.7.3 Preparation of chitosan-carbopol 971P Interpolyelectrolyte complex (IPEC) by precipitation method.

2% w/v of chitosan aqueous acetic acid solution was prepared by adding about 2gm of chitosan in 100ml of 2% v/v acetic acid solution under continuous homogenization at 1000 rpm. Then 2% carbopol 971P solutions was prepared by adding 2 gram of carbopol 971P in 100ml of distilled water and kept for hydration under continuous homogenization at 1000 rpm.

Then above prepared polymeric solution were mixed slowly under continuous homogenization at 1000 rpm which result in the formation of precipitation. Precipitation so formed was filtered under vacuum. The product was dried in hot air oven for 48hrs at 70°C and dried complex was grinded using mortar and pestle. The grinded powder was then passed through sieve no 44 and kept for further use in tablet preparation.

2.8 Method of preparation of mucoadhesive hybrid tablets of miconazole nitrate⁵.

Mucoadhesive hybrid tablets containing miconazole nitrate were prepared by direct compression technique. Different formulations of mucoadhesive hybrid tablet were prepared using specified amount of polymers and other excipients. Before going for direct compression, the entire powder blend including drug polymer and excipients were thoroughly blended in mortar and pestle for about 15 minutes. After sufficient mixing of powder blend lubricant talc was added and again mixed for additional 5 minutes. The mixture was then compressed using 6mm flat faced punch on single stroke tablet compression machine.

Table 1: Formulation chart of Miconazole nitrate hybrid mucoadhesive Tablet.

Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Miconazole nitrate	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Chitosan	--	--	50	90	--	--	--	--	--	--
Polycarbophil	40	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Chitosan: Polycarbophil(PM)	--	50	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Carbopol 971P	--	--	--	--	50	90	--	--	15	10
Chitosan:carbopol 971P(PM)	--	--	--	--	--	--	50	90	--	--
Chitosan:carbopol971P(IPEC)	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	60	70
MCC	55	45	45	5	45	5	45	5	5	5
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Where, IPEC = Interpolyelectrolyte complex, PM = Physical mixture, Total weight of each tablet = 150mg

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Tablet hardness⁶

Hardness of developed formulations F1-F10 varied from 5.2±0.22 to 6.5±0.33 kg/cm² in all the formulation indicating good physical strength with an ability to withstand physical and mechanical stress condition while handling and shipping. The results are shown in table 10.

3.2 Tablet thickness

Thickness of the developed formulation F1 to F10 varied from 4.0±0.01 to 4.3±0.05mm and average thickness was found within the range of 4 to 4.3mm. Results are shown in table 10.

3.3 Friability

Friability was in the range of 0.11 to 0.67 % for all the formulations and the friability value is less than 1% (IP limit) which ensures that formulated tablets were under the limits and can withstand physical and mechanical stress. Result is shown in table 10.

3.4 Weight variations

The maximum % deviation was found to be ± 1.00 from all the formulation. The maximum average weight of the tablet was found to be 150.8±1.00 mg. The minimum average weight of tablet was found to be 149.1±0.57mg. As none of the formulation shows a deviation 138-161.2mg (IP limit ± 7.5%) thus prepared formulation comply with the weight variation test s per I.P. Result are shown in table 10.

3.5 Uniformity of drug content⁷

The drug content in different tablet formulation was found highly uniform and in the range of 92.4±0.15% to 98.6±0.11%. This is within the limit specified by IP (i.e±10%).Optimized formulation F9 showed %drug content within specified European pharmacopoeia limits (97.5 to 102.5%). Results are given in table 10.

Drug content = Absorbance/Slope*Dilution factor*1/1000

%Drug content = Drug content/Drug dose*100

3.6 Swelling Studies⁸

The swelling results were expressed in terms of swelling index. The swelling index data of the individual formulation F1-F10 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and SVF pH 4.2 are shown in table 11 and 12 respectively.

In the initial stages, the swelling occurs very rapidly due to the entry of water via metastable pores in the tablets. This is known as hysteresis of the swelling which is followed by swelling as a result of diffusion process.

Formulation F9 and F10 containing IPEC exhibits gradual increase in swelling. Increased in concentration of IPEC in tablet, increases in swelling index which may be due to higher concentration of polymers that forms thicker gel layer around tablet and a tighter polymeric network. Formulation F9 containing gradual increase in swelling which is higher than all other formulation and also possess the similar swelling index in phosphate

buffer pH 6.8 and SVF pH 4.2. The finding indicate that the presence of IPEC along with chitosan and carbopol 971P in F9 formulation exhibit uniform pH independent swelling degree.

3.7 Mucoadhesive study⁸

In vitro Mucoadhesive testing for dosage form was evaluated by detachment force measurement.

Mucoadhesive strength of formulation F1-F10 are summarized in table 13 and represented in figure 21. Formulation F9 and F10 containing IPEC along with chitosan and carbopol971P exhibited highest mucoadhesive strength which may be due to presence of free carboxylic and amine group which are available to form bond with mucous layer.

3.8 In- vitro dissolution studies⁹

The dissolution were carried out in USP type II dissolution apparatus using phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and simulate vaginal fluid pH 4.2 as dissolution medium respectively. All the formulation from F3-F10 were tested for their release pattern for the period of 8 h and result obtained are summarized in table 16 and table 14 respectively.

F8 formulation containing the higher concentration of carbopol 971P was able to retard the drug release till 8h and also was able to oppose the disintegration action of chitosan due to strong gel network around the layer. Last two formulation (F9, F10) containing chitosan, carbopol 971P along with IPEC of chitosan and carbopol971P possess the gradual drug release pattern, above 98% drug release was observed till the end of 8h. Optimized formulation F9 was able to release 98.84 and 98.74% of miconazole nitrate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and SVF pH 4.2 at the end of 8h and thus able to give pH independent drug release.

3.9 In-vitro Diffusion Studies¹⁰

The percentage cumulative drug diffusion studies for optimized formulation F9 was done in Franz- diffusion cell using sheep buccal mucosa as the model mucous membrane and using (i.e. phosphate buffer pH 6.8, SVF pH 4.2) as the diffusion medium. It was evident from the studies that 96.46 % and 97.95 % of drug was diffused at the end of 8 h when phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and SVF ph 4.2 was used as diffusion medium respectively. This is because of its adhesive properties, good release and diffusion behavior F9 was selected for the stability studies.

Diffusion profile of F9 formulation were given in table 18, table 19 and figure 31, figure 32 respectively.

3.10 In-vivo X-ray studies¹¹

The mucoadhesion and retention property was evaluated in albino female rabbit and the X-ray photographic images were taken. Optimized formulation F-9, developed by using barium sulphate (replacing 50mg of miconazole nitrate) and was administered to rabbit. The duration of tablet in rabbit buccal and vaginal mucosa was monitored by radiograms. It was evident from the pictures that the tablet showed swelling properties and remained intact and adhered to buccal and vaginal mucosa for 8h.

3.11 Stability studies¹²

Stability studies were carried out for the most satisfactory formulation F9, at 30±2°C, 65±5%RH for two months. At the time interval of 30days and 60 days, sample was evaluated. These was no major change in the various physiochemical like hardness, drug content and in-vitro drug dissolution studies at various sampling points. Thus there was no significant difference between the initial values and the result obtained during stability studies, thus indicating stability of prepared formulation.

3.12 Preformulation study

Table 2: Solubility of Miconazole nitrate

Solvents	Solubility
Methanol	Freely soluble
Ethanol and Chloroform	Slightly soluble
Water and Ether	Very slightly soluble

3.13Melting point Determination

The melting point of miconazole nitrate was determined by using Chemline CL-725 (melting point apparatus) and melting point was found to be in range of 177-182°C.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) studies

Figure 1: DSC Thermogram of Miconazole nitrate

Figure 2: DSC Thermogram of Miconazole nitrate + Polymer

3.14 IR -SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of miconazole nitrate

Table 3: FTIR interpretation of miconazole nitrate

S.NO	Functional group	Wave number cm ⁻¹
1	CH=CH	3062
2	C-H	2934
3	C-O-C	1267
4	C=N	1424
5	C-Cl	745

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of MN+ carbopol 971P

Table 4: FTIR interpretation of MN + carbopol 971P

S.NO	Functional group	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)
1	CH=CH	3099
2	C-H	2991
3	C-O-C	1176
4	C=N	1468
5	C-Cl	747

Figure 5: FTIR spectra of MN+ Polycarbophil

Table 5: FTIR interpretation of MN+ Polycarbophil

S.NO	Functional group	Wavenumber(cm-1)
1	CH=CH	3067
2	C-H	2927
3	C-O-C	1255
4	C=N	1474
5	C-Cl	745

Figure 6: FTIR spectra of MN + Chitosan-Carbopol971P IPEC

Table 6: FTIR interpretation of MN+ Chitosan-carbopol971P IPEC

S.NO	Functional group	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)
1	O-H	3491
2	N-H	3340
3	C=O	1731
4	C-O	1196
5	C-H	2958

Characterization of IPEC by FTIR

Figure 7: FTIR spectra of chitosan in Wavenumber 2000-1000 cm⁻¹

Figure 8: FTIR spectra of chitosan in Wavenumber 1800 – 1400⁻¹cm

Figure 9: FTIR spectra of carbopol971P in Wavenumber 2000- 1000 cm⁻¹

Figure 10: FTIR spectra of carbopol971P in Wavenumber 1800-1400 cm⁻¹

Figure 11: FTIR spectra of IPEC in Wavenumber 2000-1000 cm⁻¹

Figure 12: FTIR spectra of IPEC in Wavenumber 1800-1400cm⁻¹

Standard curve of miconazole nitrate

Figure 13: Absorption maxima of miconazole nitrate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Table 7: Standard calibration data for miconazole nitrate

Sl. NO.	Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance *
1	10	0.139±0.018
2	20	0.317±0.015
3	30	0.436±0.023
4	40	0.567±0.011
5	50	0.677±0.022

* All values are mean of three readings ± S.D

Figure 14: Calibration curve of miconazole nitrate in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Figure 15: Absorption maxima of miconazole nitrate in SVF pH 4.2.

Table 8: Calibration curve data of miconazole nitrate in SVF pH4.2.

S.NO	Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance *
1	25	0.113±0.013
2	50	0.227±0.015
3	75	0.322±0.012
4	100	0.446±0.016
5	125	0.549±0.018

* All values are mean of three readings ± S.D

Figure 16: Calibration curve of miconazole nitrate in SVF pH 4.2.

3.14 Precompressional parameters

Micromeretic properties of F1-F10

Table 9: Preformulation studies of F1-F10

Formulation	Angle of repose (°) Mean ± SD	Bulk density (gm/ml) Mean ± SD	Tapped density(gm/ml) Mean ± SD	Carr's index (%) Mean± SD	Hausner's ratio Mean± SD
F1	33.63±0.80	0.351±0.003	0.398±0.01	11.80±0.63	1.13±0.01
F2	31.32±1.07	0.354±0.001	0.388±0.02	8.76±0.47	0.78±0.05
F3	32.06±0.25	0.356±0.003	0.392±0.06	9.18±0.48	1.10±0.09
F4	33.21±0.35	0.328±0.001	0.369±0.05	11.11±0.83	1.09±0.05
F5	34.34±0.51	0.368±0.005	0.398±0.02	7.53±0.68	1.08±0.02
F6	29.83±0.27	0.343±0.006	0.391±0.04	12.27±0.42	1.13±0.02
F7	30.19±0.15	0.328±0.004	0.372±0.01	11.82±0.56	1.13±0.02
F8	29.78±0.15	0.353±0.005	0.385±0.02	8.31±0.66	1.09±0.02
F9	27.37±0.16	0.319±0.005	0.466±0.01	9.33±0.56	1.13±0.02
F10	29.21±0.35	0.327±0.001	0.508±0.01	12.2±0.45	1.12±0.02

3.15 Post-compression evaluation data

Table 10: Post compression evaluation data of F1-F10

Formulation Code	Weight(mg)* n= 20	Thickness(mm)* n= 10	Hardness(kg/cm) ² * n= 10	Friability n= 20	% Drug content*
F1	149.2±0.53	4.2±0.03	5.5±0.22	0.67	93.6±0.12
F2	150.0±0.78	4.3±0.02	5.8±0.42	0.54	92.4 ±0.25
F3	149.5±0.55	4.1±0.01	5.4±0.34	0.62	95.9 ±0.18
F4	149.1±0.57	4.3±0.05	5.3±0.23	0.54	96.4±0.15
F5	149.3±0.42	4.0±0.04	5.2±0.32	0.51	97.2±0.12
F6	150.2±0.86	4.1±0.02	6.0±0.31	0.15	97.8±0.15
F7	149.2±0.26	4.3±0.02	6.3±0.52	0.11	93.7±0.14
F8	149.6±0.42	4.2±0.03	6.2±0.61	0.15	94.3±0.12
F9	150.0±0.82	4.0±0.01	6.5±0.53	0.11	98.6 ±0.11
F10	149.5±0.55	4.1±0.02	5.3±2	0.12	98.4 ±0.15

* All values are mean of three readings ± SD

3.16 Swelling studies Data

All values are mean of three readings \pm SD

Table 11: Swelling index data of F1-F10 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Formulation	1h	2hr	3h	4h	5h	6h	7h	8h
F1	20 \pm 0.35	35 \pm 0.54	70 \pm 0.65					
F2	19 \pm 0.42	41 \pm 0.49	76 \pm 0.55					
F3	180 \pm 0.43	232 \pm 0.57	341 \pm 0.33	411 \pm 0.58	453 \pm 0.37	485 \pm 0.53	518 \pm 0.63	523 \pm 0.35
F4	204 \pm 0.34	277 \pm 0.56	389 \pm 0.65	449 \pm 0.57	498 \pm 0.33	532 \pm 0.24	543 \pm 0.76	551 \pm 0.35
F5	372 \pm 0.57	421 \pm 0.33	453 \pm 0.36	523 \pm 0.25	571 \pm 0.18			
F6	312 \pm 0.45	394 \pm 0.26	435 \pm 0.27	486 \pm 0.79	532 \pm 0.27	527 \pm 0.67	593 \pm 0.78	611 \pm 0.34
F7	94 \pm 0.67	102 \pm 0.23	125 \pm 0.65	177 \pm 0.67	234 \pm 0.78	297 \pm 0.57	310 \pm 0.67	352 \pm 0.67
F8	99 \pm 0.35	142 \pm 0.56	162 \pm 0.78	213 \pm 0.38	289 \pm 0.67	334 \pm 0.28	364 \pm 0.34	382 \pm 0.73
F9	96 \pm 0.76	201 \pm 0.47	372 \pm 0.34	487 \pm 0.79	638 \pm 0.45	723 \pm 0.87	863 \pm 0.56	946 \pm 0.47
F10	78 \pm 0.65	188 \pm 0.43	275 \pm 0.84	398 \pm 0.37	538 \pm 0.37	699 \pm 0.37	738 \pm 0.37	814 \pm 0.25

Figure 17: Swelling index graph of F1-F5 in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Figure 18: Swelling index graph of F6-F10 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Table 12: Swelling index data of F1-F10 in SVF pH 4.2

Formulation code	1h	2h	3h	4h	5h	6h	7h	8h
F1	75±0.34	95±0.24	126±0.27	150±0.21				
F2	90±0.41	188±0.56	225±0.52	287±0.53				
F3	221±0.35	282±0.43	374±0.54	441±0.67	498±0.26			
F4	327±0.52	382±0.34	428±0.56	492±0.58	498±0.36	528±0.54		
F5	338±0.35	423±0.56	487±0.34	554±0.58	598±0.45	614±0.34		
F6	352±0.54	402±0.65	455±0.35	506±0.36	562±0.37	592±0.27	623±0.32	671±0.39
F7	94±0.17	112±0.34	129±0.26	181±0.45	234±0.45	277±0.45	310±0.25	352±0.23
F8	102±0.36	134±0.27	164±0.35	227±0.28	280±0.27	334±0.34	365±0.45	396±0.56
F9	98±0.13	205±0.28	375±0.57	489±0.37	641±0.34	726±0.27	865±0.53	948±0.43
F10	79±0.18	189±0.38	278±0.27	398±0.26	537±0.29	698±0.46	738±0.62	816±0.67

Figure 19: Swelling index graph of F1-F10 in SVF pH 4.2.

Figure 20: Swelling index graph of F6-F10 in SVF pH 4.2.

3.17 *In-vitro* mucoadhesive strength

Table 13: Mucoadhesive strength of F1-F10

Formulation code	Mucoadhesive strength(Gm) (Mean±SD)
F1	25±0.01
F2	37±0.02
F3	42±0.03
F4	45±0.01
F5	52±0.03
F6	58±0.03
F7	63±0.04
F8	59±0.03
F9	68±0.01
F10	64±0.01

Figure 21: Mucoadhesive strength graph of F1-F10.

Figure 22: Modified weight balance apparatus

3.18 In- vitro dissolution studies

Table 14: In-vitro dissolution studies of F3-F10 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Time (h)	F3% Mean±SD	F4% Mean±SD	F5% Mean±SD	F6% Mean±SD	F7% Mean±SD	F8% Mean±SD	F9% Mean±SD	F10% Mean±SD
1	28.55±0.69	28.45±0.97	27.99±0.34	19.42±0.26	38.44±0.57	20.92±0.75	10.68±0.75	15.26
2	35.05±0.82	54.05±0.28	33.54±0.71	26.41±0.33	52.09±1.48	36.43±0.61	20.84	27.20
3	62.98±0.25	70.25±0.29	49.86±0.29	41.56±0.44	67.19±0.16	44.72±0.82	33.12	36.36
4	78.26±0.32	90.26±0.90	69.13±0.13	58.19±0.40	83.59±0.44	53.54±0.60	47.81	57.7
5	84.59±0.27	93.58±0.32	85.94±0.54	67.59±1.40	89.37±0.27	67.76±0.93	60.37	66.49
6	----	----	89.18±0.18	82.22±1.70	94.63±0.58	78.83±0.34	78.78	81.18
7	----	----	90.39±0.33	91.82±0.26	95.95±0.17	84.69±0.38	87.34	90.36
8	----	----	----	---	---	97.71±0.14	98.74	96.80

Table 15: kinetic modelling for drug dissolution profiles of F3-F10 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

KINETIC MODEL	PARAMETER	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
ZERO ORDER	REGRESSION	0.965	0.957	0.947	0.973	0.898	0.994	0.995	0.988
FIRST ORDER	REGRESSION	0.966	0.967	0.949	0.918	0.985	0.800	0.772	0.900
HIGUCHI	REGRESSION	0.945	0.982	0.948	0.973	0.969	0.984	0.973	0.981
KORSMEYER – PEPPAS	SLOPE	0.741	0.760	0.691	0.845	0.505	0.726	0.952	0.929
	REGRESSION	0.931	0.982	0.947	0.977	0.983	0.994	0.997	0.991

Table 16: *In-vitro* dissolution studies in of F3-F10 in Simulated vaginal fluid pH 4.2

Time (h)	F3% Mean±SD*	F4% Mean±SD*	F5% Mean±SD*	F6% Mean±SD*	F7% Mean±SD*	F8% Mean±SD*	F9% Mean±SD*	F10% Mean±SD
1	28.55±0.69	28.45±0.97	27.99±0.34	19.42±0.26	38.44±0.57	20.92±0.75	10.68	15.26
2	35.05±0.82	54.05±0.28	33.54±0.71	26.41±0.33	52.09±1.48	36.43±0.61	20.84	27.20
3	62.98±0.25	70.25±0.29	49.86±0.29	41.56±0.44	67.19±0.16	44.72±0.82	33.12	36.36
4	78.26±0.32	90.26±0.90	69.13±0.13	58.19±0.40	83.59±0.44	53.54±0.60	47.81	57.7
5	84.59±0.27	93.58±0.32	85.94±0.54	67.59±1.40	89.37±0.27	67.76±0.93	60.37	66.49
6	----	----	89.18±0.18	82.22±1.70	94.63±0.58	78.83±0.34	78.78	81.18
7	----	----	90.39±0.33	91.82±0.26	95.95±0.17	84.69±0.38	87.34	90.36
8	----	----	----	---	---	97.71±0.14	98.74	96.80

*All values are mean of three reading ± SD

Table 17: Kinetic modelling of drug release profile from F3-F10 in Simulated vaginal fluid pH 4.2

KINETIC MODEL	PARAMETER	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
ZERO ORDER	REGRESSION	0.965	0.957	0.947	0.973	0.898	0.994	0.995	0.988
FIRST ORDER	REGRESSION	0.966	0.967	0.949	0.918	0.985	0.800	0.772	0.900
HIGUCHI	REGRESSION	0.945	0.982	0.948	0.973	0.969	0.984	0.973	0.981
KORSMEYER PEPPAS	SLOPE	0.931	0.760	0.691	0.845	0.504	0.726	0.985	0.927
	REGRESSION	0.931	0.982	0.947	0.977	0.981	0.994	0.997	0.991

3.19 *In-vitro* diffusion studies

Table 18: *In-vitro* diffusion data of F9 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Time(h)	Drug release (Mean ±SD)
1	16.3±0.56
2	32.9±0.63
3	50.44±0.75
4	65.16±0.47
5	78.38±0.56
6	85.70±0.38
7	91.88±0.28
8	96.46±0.29

Figure 31: Diffusion data of F9 in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Table 19: In-vitro diffusion data of f9 in simulated vaginal fluid pH 4.2

Time(h)	Drug release (Mean ±SD)
1	12.35±0.58
2	23.84±0.68
3	37.35±0.78
4	53.28±0.49
5	69.68±0.58
6	86.92±0.35
7	90.97±0.32
8	97.95±0.33

Figure 32: Diffusion pattern of F9 in SVF pH 4.2.

3.20 Stability studies

Table 20: Physicochemical parameters of F9 after 2 months stability studies

Time(Days)	Stability condition	Hardness(kg/cm2)*	Drug content%*
0	30±2°C,65±5%RH	6.5±0.331	98.6±0.112
30	30±2°C,65±5%RH	6.3±0.262	98.0±0.183
60	30±2°C,65±5%RH	6.1±0.283	97.7C0.146

*All values are mean of three readings ± SD

Table 21: Drug release studies of Formulation-9 after 2 months of stability studies

Time (h)	%CDR After 30 days*	%CDR After 60 days*
1	9.5±0.590	9.2±0.481
2	18.6±0.484	17.4±0.362
3	30.74±0.632	28.34±0.674
4	38.32±0.532	39.16±0.431
5	48.9±0.438	45.3±0.236
6	68.9±0.215	67.2±0.362
7	85.4±0.312	83.4±0.153
8	95.3±0.632	94.2±0.578

* All values are mean of three readings ± SD

4. CONCLUSION

There is strong prophylactic and clinical need to develop new solid dosage form for candidacies with desired characteristics such as better therapeutic efficacy, retention for intended interval, patient flexibility with cost effective medication. The mucoadhesive hybrid drug delivery system developed viz., Interpolyelectrolyte complexes have demonstrated their superiority and suitability for buccal and vaginal route for candidacies. Thus the study shows that the developed system has a great appeal for the convenient treatment of candidacies that may be explored in improving the limitations of existing drug delivery system.

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